

CS 597 Individual Study Report

Exploring Color Spaces in the Context of Chemistry Education

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1 Introduction

1.1 Digital Molecule Maker

Chemical synthesis has a wide range of applications in health, energy and sustainability, such as discovering new drugs and more efficient and stable organic photovoltaic (OPV) cells. Traditionally, chemical synthesis of functional molecules relies on expert intuition and iterative testing. To democratize and accelerate this process, the Molecule Maker Lab Institute (MMLI) provides a new AI-enabled platform that facilitates exploration and experimentation for experts and non-experts alike.

Digital Molecule Maker (DMM), one of the projects at MMLI, will be a training ground for the next generation of scientists and innovators. DMM is a web-application that provides a user interface for interactive exploration of building-block-based chemical synthesis, combining the predictive power of computation with automated synthesis in the lab. As shown in the screenshots (Figure 1), students can drag three types of blocks — start, middle and end — from the left-side block tray into the workspace. The dataset currently available in DMM for exploration contains properties of each molecular block, including molecular weight and the wavelength of maximum absorbance (λ_{max}). Students can click on the molecule widget in the workspace to reveal the predicted properties of the combined molecule, computed from those of the constituent blocks. Finally, finished molecules could be submitted to the backend, which is connected to the lab where the actual synthesis could be performed according to the submitted specifications. Students could also request photos of the synthesized molecules in solution.

1.2 Function Mode

As an educational tool, DMM faces a major challenge: Chemical synthesis is an extremely slow process. To combine three molecular blocks requires two chemical reactions, each taking about 6 hours to complete. While students do receive feedback from the dropdown summary and the pictures sent from the lab, these forms of feedback are less than ideal: The numbers in the summary may not make much sense to students who likely don't have prior knowledge, and a 12-hour turnaround time is simply too long for the feedback to be conducive to students' learning. Furthermore, due to cost concerns, it might be unrealistic to synthesize all block combinations students want to explore.

Function Mode, a new feature of DMM, aims to solve this problem by providing users with visual feedback through real-time simulation, which avoids the delays and costs incurred by the actual chemical synthesis. Compared to numerical values, visual representations of chemical properties could convey chemical intuitions more effectively, thereby helping students to accelerate their progress toward molecules with desired properties. With the current dataset, one objective is for students to create molecules that absorb light within specific wavelength ranges. For this task, it would be helpful to use the perceived

Figure 1. User interface of DMM

colors of molecular blocks as a visual cue. As shown in the screenshots (Figure 2), students can select color filters on the left-side panel, and the molecular block tray will be updated to only show the blocks that could help achieve those perceived colors. As blocks are added, removed and replaced in the workspace, the list updates dynamically, and the molecule widget in the workspace gradually shifts color, reflecting the underlying changes in chemical properties.

At the heart of the Function Mode feature, including both the visual feedback and the dynamic filtering, is the question: How do we translate between the chemical properties and the perceived color of a molecule? And perhaps more importantly, how do we do so efficiently and practically? Our attempts to answer these questions will be the focus of this report.

2 Background: Color and Chemistry

From a color science perspective, color perception is determined by light absorption spectra in the visible range. To calculate absorption spectra, chemists use the density-functional theory (DFT), which is based on computational quantum mechanical models of the electronic structure of molecules. Although DFT is an exact theory, predictions made by DFT are not necessarily accurate, as implementations of DFT rely on approximations. Furthermore, according to chemists, many other factors could also affect perceived color, such as bond rotations, chemical impurities, and interactions with different types of solvents.

It would be infeasible to account for all these variables, but fortunately, an approximation suffices in the context of DMM, where color only serves as a guidance to encourage students to explore the exact chemical properties. For the real-time computation in DMM, chemists on the team have decided to use the empirical Woodward–Fieser rules [3], which describe how the presence of various kinds of molecular structures can lead to shifts in the wavelength of the absorption maximum (λ_{max}). The λ_{max} values for all molecular blocks in the dataset have already been estimated, and the data is available to the browser

Figure 2. User interface of DMM: Function Mode

at runtime. Given an estimated λ_{max} value, we can predict the corresponding perceived color in various ways. In this study, we explored two methods: integration, which will be discussed in Section 3, and interpolation, which will be discussed in Section 4.

3 Integration of CIE XYZ Color Matching Functions

3.1 Model

In the CIE color model, the empirically determined color matching functions $\bar{x}(\lambda)$, $\bar{y}(\lambda)$ and $\bar{z}(\lambda)$ describe a standard observer's chromatic responses to light of different wavelengths. The XYZ tristimulus values are defined as the integral of the point-wise product of spectral intensity and the color matching functions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 X &= \frac{1}{N} \int_0^{\infty} (1 - \text{absorbance}(\lambda; \lambda_{max})) \bar{x}(\lambda) d\lambda \\
 Y &= \frac{1}{N} \int_0^{\infty} (1 - \text{absorbance}(\lambda; \lambda_{max})) \bar{y}(\lambda) d\lambda \\
 Z &= \frac{1}{N} \int_0^{\infty} (1 - \text{absorbance}(\lambda; \lambda_{max})) \bar{z}(\lambda) d\lambda
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$N = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \bar{y}(\lambda) d\lambda$$

Although we can't derive the entire absorption spectrum from λ_{max} alone, we nevertheless estimated the overall shape of normalized absorbance to be a Gaussian function of wavelength:

$$\text{absorbance}(\lambda; \lambda_{max}) \approx e^{-(\lambda - \lambda_{max})^2 / 75}$$

Finally, for display in browser, we need to convert the color from XYZ space to RGB space through a linear transformation, which is determined by setting the CIE standard illuminant D65 as reference white,

$$\begin{pmatrix} R \\ G \\ B \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 2.0413690 & -0.5649464 & -0.3446944 \\ -0.9692660 & 1.8760108 & 0.0415560 \\ 0.0134474 & -0.1183897 & 1.0154096 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{pmatrix}$$

3.2 Implementation

[4] introduced a simple analytical approximations for CIE color matching functions using multi-lobe piecewise continuous Gaussians, which are more clearly described by code than formulas:

```
function x(lambda) {
  const t1 = (lambda - 442.0) * (lambda < 442.0 ? 0.0624 : 0.0374);
  const t2 = (lambda - 599.8) * (lambda < 599.8 ? 0.0264 : 0.0323);
  const t3 = (lambda - 501.1) * (lambda < 501.1 ? 0.049 : 0.0382);
  return (
    0.362 * Math.exp(-0.5 * t1 * t1) +
    1.056 * Math.exp(-0.5 * t2 * t2) -
    0.065 * Math.exp(-0.5 * t3 * t3)
  );
}

function y(lambda) {
  const t1 = (lambda - 568.8) * (lambda < 568.8 ? 0.0213 : 0.0247);
  const t2 = (lambda - 530.9) * (lambda < 530.9 ? 0.0613 : 0.0322);
  return (
    0.821 * Math.exp(-0.5 * t1 * t1) +
    0.286 * Math.exp(-0.5 * t2 * t2)
  );
}

function z(lambda) {
  const t1 = (lambda - 437.0) * (lambda < 437.0 ? 0.0845 : 0.0278);
  const t2 = (lambda - 459.0) * (lambda < 459.0 ? 0.0385 : 0.0725);
  return (
    1.217 * Math.exp(-0.5 * t1 * t1) +
    0.681 * Math.exp(-0.5 * t2 * t2)
  );
}
```

The integral from 0 to ∞ is simply implemented as a discrete sum over integer λ values in the visible range:

```
function lambdaMaxToXYZ(lambdaMax) {
  let X = 0, Y = 0, Z = 0, N = 0;
  for (let l = 380; l <= 780; ++l) {
    X += x(l) * (1 - absorbance(l, lambdaMax));
    Y += y(l) * (1 - absorbance(l, lambdaMax));
    Z += z(l) * (1 - absorbance(l, lambdaMax));
  }
}
```


Figure 3. Color spectrum computed from the numerical integration of color-matching functions

```

    N += y(1);
}
return [X / N, Y / N, Z / N];
}

```

3.3 Results and Issues

Figure 1 shows the colors of the absorbed and transmitted (or reflected) light computed from our Gaussian model peaking at each λ_{max} in the visible range. The first spectrum visualizes the absorbed colors, and the second one the perceived colors, which could be thought of as complementary to the absorbed colors. We can clearly identify the three additive primaries (red, green, blue) and the three subtractive primaries (cyan, magenta, yellow) in the two spectrums, respectively. This confirms the overall correctness of our integration method.

It is worth noting that there is a major shortcoming of this method for which there is no obvious solution: The actual absorption spectrum might have multiple peaks, as is the case for chlorophyll, the green pigment in plants, whose absorption spectrum peaks at both blue and red, as shown in Figure 2. It is impossible to infer the location of multiple peaks from a single λ_{max} max value, and therefore our model cannot account for such cases. The spectrum of perceived colors shown in Figure 1 confirms the impossibility of producing the color green with a simple Gaussian model.

4 Linear Interpolation of Subtractive Primaries

4.1 Model

The perceived color spectrum produced by our first method could be further approximated by a gradient between the subtractive primaries, which is conceptually simpler and computationally more efficient. In the case of linear gradient, this is achieved using the method of piecewise linear interpolation. Formally, given a list of color stops $\{\lambda_i \mapsto C_i\}$ that maps a finite set of wavelengths to colors, the interpolated color for any $\lambda_i \leq \lambda \leq \lambda_{i+1}$ is

$$C(\lambda) = C_i + \frac{\lambda - \lambda_i}{\lambda_{i+1} - \lambda_i}(C_{i+1} - C_i) = \frac{(\lambda_{i+1} - \lambda)C_i + (\lambda - \lambda_i)C_{i+1}}{\lambda_{i+1} - \lambda_i}$$

There are two questions we must answer first:

1. In which color space should we perform the interpolation? Since the transformation between color spaces are generally non-linear, a linear interpolation in one space would not be linear in another.
2. What color stops (λ_i, C_i) should we use?

Figure 4. Absorption spectrum of chlorophyll [2]

4.2 Background: Color Spaces

Whereas XYZ and RGB tristimulus values reflect our low-level physiological responses to light of different wavelengths, color spaces with luminance and chromaticity components more closely align with our high-level perception of color, which makes them better suited for our task at hand. In this study, we experimented with three such color spaces: CIELAB, CIELCh_{ab}, and HSL, all of which require non-linear transformations from XYZ and RGB. The following sections (4.2.1 - 4.2.3) are common textbook knowledge, included here only for reference.

4.2.1 CIELAB ($L^*a^*b^*$)

CIELAB values are computed from the differences between XYZ components. Using a non-linear function

$$f(t) = [t > \delta^3] \cdot \sqrt[3]{t} + [t \leq \delta^3] \cdot \left(\frac{t}{3\delta^2} + \frac{4}{29} \right), \text{ where } \delta = \frac{6}{29},$$

and the XYZ components of a reference white, such as D65 ($X_n = 95.0489$, $Y_n = 100$, $Z_n = 108.8840$), the L^* (luminance), a^* (green-red), and b^* (blue-yellow) components of a color are computed as

$$\begin{aligned} L^* &= 116f\left(\frac{Y}{Y_n}\right) - 16 \\ a^* &= 500\left(f\left(\frac{X}{X_n}\right) - f\left(\frac{Y}{Y_n}\right)\right) \\ b^* &= 200\left(f\left(\frac{Y}{Y_n}\right) - f\left(\frac{Z}{Z_n}\right)\right) \end{aligned}$$

4.2.2 CIELCh_{ab} (LCh)

CIELCh_{ab} is simply CIELAB expressed in cylindrical coordinates: The luminance component L is the same as in CIELAB, the chroma (relative saturation) component C^* is the radius in the a^*b^* plane, and the hue component h° is the angle measured in degrees in the a^*b^* plane, i.e.

$$C^* = \sqrt{a^{*2} + b^{*2}}, \quad h^\circ = \text{atan2}(b^*, a^*)$$

4.2.3 HSL

HSL, which stands for "hue, saturation, lightness", is computed from the differences between RGB components. First, we find the maximum M , minimum m , and chroma C from RGB components

$$M = \max(R, G, B), \quad m = \min(R, G, B), \quad C = M - m$$

The hue component H , ranging from 0° to 360° , is computed based on which RGB component is dominant:

$$H = 60^\circ \cdot \left[[M = R] \left(\frac{G - B}{C} \bmod 6 \right) + [M = G] \left(\frac{B - R}{C} + 2 \right) + [M = B] \left(\frac{R - G}{C} + 4 \right) \right]$$

The luminance component L and saturation component S are simply computed as

$$L = \frac{M + m}{2}, \quad S = \frac{C}{1 - |2L - 1|}$$

4.3 Implementation

For this study, we considered both additive and subtractive primaries for color stops. The following table lists their corresponding wavelengths used in our interpolation. It's worth pointing out that these specific values have no particular physical meanings and could be adjusted as needed.

Color C_i	Wavelength λ_i (nm)
yellow (Y)	440
red (R)	499
magenta (M)	530
blue (B)	592.5
cyan (C)	622.5

We used the JavaScript library D3 [1] to perform linear interpolation in various color spaces and to visualize the results in CIELAB and CIELCh_{ab} coordinates. Instead of using the default `d3.piecewise` function, which places color stops at equally spaced intervals, we manually implemented the piecewise interpolator to allow for adjusting color stop positions based on estimated wavelength ranges. The outline of our implementation is as follows:

```
function interpolate(lambda) {
  let prev = null;
  let next = null;

  for (const cur of SubtractivePrimaries) {
    if (cur.peak <= lambda && (!prev || cur.peak > prev.peak)) {
      prev = cur;
    }
  }
}
```

```

    }
    if (cur.peak >= lambda && (!next || cur.peak < next.peak)) {
        next = cur;
    }
}

const color1 = d3.color(prev?.name ?? "#EEEEEE");
const color2 = d3.color(next?.name ?? "#EEEEEE");
const lambda1 = prev?.peak ?? LAMBDA_MIN;
const lambda2 = next?.peak ?? LAMBDA_MAX;

const interpolator = Interpolator(color1, color2);
const t = Math.min(1, Math.max(0, (lambda - lambda1) / (lambda2 - lambda1)));
return d3.color(interpolator(t));
}

```

Only the integer values of λ in the visible range are included.

5 Comparison of Results

In each figure below, the first color spectrum is the output from our numerical integration method, and the second spectrum is the output from our piecewise linear interpolation method. Also included in each figure are two plots in the a^*-b^* plane of the CIELAB color space and the C^*-h° plane of the CIELCh_{ab} color space, respectively. In each plot, the gray curve is traced by integration and the white curve is traced by piecewise linear interpolation. The arrows on each curve indicate the direction of motion as λ_{max} increases, and the density of arrows represents the rate at which color changes with respect to shifts in λ_{max} , i.e.

$$\left\| \frac{d}{d\lambda_{max}} (a^*(\lambda_{max}), b^*(\lambda_{max})) \right\| \text{ and } \left\| \frac{d}{d\lambda_{max}} (C^*(\lambda_{max}), h^\circ(\lambda_{max})) \right\|.$$

One significant distinction between the color spectra generated through integration and interpolation lies in their smoothness. With integration, the parametric curve representing the color spectrum is smooth in CIELAB. With piecewise linear interpolation, however, each color stop results in a brighter band in the color spectrum and a corresponding corner in the curve. (Interestingly, interpolating between the three subtractive primaries (yellow, magenta, cyan) in the HSL color space actually produces two extra bands/corners at red and blue, resulting in nearly the same spectrum/curve as if five color stops were used.) Furthermore, the speeds of change in color as measured in CIELAB with respect to λ_{max} in two adjacent wavelength intervals could be drastically different, as can be observed in the graphs through the abrupt changes in arrow densities between adjacent curve segments, due to the non-uniform distances between the color stops in the CIELAB space.

The lack of smoothness is a consequence of the interpolator being piecewise linear. To ensure smoothness we could instead use a spline curve with a continuous first derivative in a color space of our choosing:

$$C(\lambda_{max}) = \sum_{i=0}^n B_i(\lambda_{max}) P_i$$

For basis functions B_i , we could use any smooth functions, such as Bernstein basis polynomials (i.e. Bézier basis functions) $B_{i,n}$ (after normalizing λ_{max} to the $[0, 1]$ range) or B-spline basis functions $N_{i,k}$ of degree

k (with an appropriate knot vector, possibly based on wavelength ranges associated with color categories). The color stops we want the curve to pass through give us a system of linear equations,

$$C_j = \sum_{i=0}^n B_i(\lambda_j) P_i,$$

from which we can solve (e.g. using least-squares fitting) for the control points P_i . Alternatively, we could also simply solve for a single high-degree polynomial curve passing through all color stops.

Apart from theoretical possibilities, there are also important practical factors to consider: For the current mode of interaction, the user interface only displays a single color at a time, therefore a user can't actually perceive the smoothness, or the lack thereof, in the color spectrum. Furthermore, we could simply convey the illusion of smoothness with CSS transitions supported by browser rendering engines, which performs yet another layer of linear interpolation.

6 Conclusion

In this study, we explored two approximation methods for predicting perceived colors of molecules in the context of DMM and chemistry education. Taking into account the target audience, use cases and future maintainability of DMM, we opted for the method of piecewise linear interpolation of subtractive primaries in the HSL space, as it produces a color spectrum sufficiently effective for educational purposes with a relatively straightforward implementation.

The Function Mode feature is currently undergoing active testing in high school and undergraduate classroom settings for in-class activities. The feedback obtained will be utilized to extend this feature to incorporate more datasets, such as the OPV dataset, and explore additional modes of interaction. As a future improvement, we are also considering replacing Woodward–Fieser rules with a more precise model that accounts for the possibility of multiple peaks in the absorption spectrum.

References

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- [4] C. Wyman, P.-P. Sloan, and P. Shirley. Simple analytic approximations to the CIE XYZ color matching functions. *Journal of Computer Graphics Techniques (JCGT)*, 2(2):1–11, July 2013.

Figure 5. Y-R-M-B-C interpolation in RGB space

Figure 6. Y-R-M-B-C interpolation in HSL space

Figure 7. Y-R-M-B-C interpolation in CIELAB space

Figure 8. Y-R-M-B-C interpolation in CIELCh_{ab} space

Figure 9. Y-M-C interpolation in RGB space

Figure 10. Y-M-C interpolation in HSL space

Figure 11. Y-M-C interpolation in CIELAB space

Figure 12. Y-M-C interpolation in CIElCh_{ab} space